

A Study of the Synthesis of Consequentialism and Formalism in Myanmar Culture

Cho Cho Myint*

Abstract

This paper is an attempt to solve the problem why Consequentialism and Formalism are combination in Myanmar Culture. In the Myanmar culture accepts rationalism after analyzing the Consequentialism and Formalism accord with time and place. The moral conducts that should be practiced for the benefit of human society are important together with intellect that can rationalize the existing situations. The descriptive method is used in making a literature review and the evaluative method based on the principles of analysis and synthesis.

Introduction

Ethics is a normative study as it lays emphasis upon norms, standards and principle of human conduct. Human society needs moral principle to guide individuals to know the difference between right and wrong, good and evil. The moral standards of men depend upon the stage of social development and upon the level of intelligence and knowledge available at the time. Hence, social progress of mankind largely depends upon the moral awareness of the individual. In a society, mutual trust in each other is vital for the development of that society.

Any person who has concern for culture and civilization will concern himself with practical and ethical issues, for ethics has to do with human conduct. The need for ethics arises from the fact that man is not perfect by nature: he has to train himself to be good. Thus morality becomes the important aspect of living. Morality is an observance of the law of wholesome living.

The criteria of ethical conduct, according to *Theravāda* Buddhist doctrine are based on the harmonious social relations of human beings and they reflect human values of social life. The right or wrong and the good or bad are determined by the human intellect that can differentiate various kinds of conduct under different conditions.

The Concept of Formalism in Western Tradition

The formalist view states that the concept of right comes from a moral law or law of duty. A moral law is that which ought to be. Any action done without a sense of duty is not a moral action. Any action done without any proper motive is not right action. In fact Immanuel Kant (1724-1804), the foremost proponent of the formalist view holds that if an action is done out of good will then it is moral regardless of whether the consequences are good or bad. Here it is held that the end result has no moral significance. It is the motive that determines morality.

According to the Western tradition, the good life is the life which leads to the harmonious development of the distinctive characteristics for humans as social beings. To do what is right is the duty of each individual. When we judge an action to be right, we feel it to be our duty to do it.

Kant emphasizes not the consequences of an act but the intent or motive behind it. He said that if one chooses to act in a certain way to achieve a specific and then that is not moral conduct. These are acts for survival to avoid pain and gain pleasure. These decisions are non-

* Dr., Professor & Head, Department of Philosophy, Bago University.

moral for they arise out of human nature. We must find a principle that is universal for a moral precept is one that is universalizable.

According to D.R.Bali's , exposition of Kant's ethical view, he used the term good and right to indicate goodness in itself and not for a purpose or a desired end. Goodness does not depend upon the consequences of action. Kant believed that nothing was good in itself except a good will. He defined 'will' as the uniquely human ability to act in accordance with rules, laws or principles, regardless of interest or consequence. Kant emphasized the importance of 'goodwill'. When an action conforms to a moral principle, it is said to be right. Formalists claim that right means conducting oneself in accordance with the moral principle. The formalists holds that motive alone determine morality.

The Concept of Consequentialism in Western Tradition

The consequentialist view that holds that an action must be judged as moral or not moral, depending on the results or consequences that follow. If the end result has merit then it is right and moral, whereas if it lacks merit then it is neither right nor moral. The consequentialist asserts that the moral quality of an action must be judged by its consequences. According to Jeremy Bentham, 'right' is considered 'to be productive to the general happiness. John Stuart Mill asserts that ' actions are right in proportion as they tend to promote happiness.

The place of motive and consequences in determining the rightness or wrongness of action again is a matter of dispute between the formalist and consequentialist. The formalist holds that motive alone and the consequentialist holds that consequences or merit alone, determine alone.

A study of Western tradition shows that the concept of right and merit is considered important in relation to moral conduct. Consequentialists define that the right action has action has good result or merit. By the acceptance and practicing of the concept of right and consequence ,man can be freed from social conflicts and in any society.

Combination of Cconsequentialism and Formalism

Ethics is essentially concerned with human attitudes and behaviours which are standardized as being right or wrong, good or bad, and that one should do or should not. Based on these criterions, ethics assess systematically the varied human behaviours and actions and highlight a unity which underlies the differences of different societal actions.

Man is a social being and he cannot live alone. He lives together with other people. The social relation among the members of a community may lead to contradiction and dispute, unless there is moral discipline agreed by the members of the community. These principles arose in the ancient human society as customs which over time because the ethical rules. These in any human societies, there are ethical rules for harmonious social relation. Ethics is the systematic analysis and evaluation of the differing moral principles.

Not all the man's actions for all the day are included in ethics. The behaviours that can be regards as being right or wrong and good or bad are concerned with ethical conducts. There can be various actions which are concerned with ethics. As man is a combination of mind and body, his behaviour may be motivated either by motive which is mind-base or by physical consequence related to body. Motive can be good or bad motive. Likewise, consequence may be good or bad. By combining motive and consequence, there can be four different behaviours as follows:

1. An act must be done of out good will, and may result in good consequences.
2. Although an act may be done out of good will, it may result in evil consequences.
3. Although an act is done out of evil will, it may lead to good consequences.
4. An act is done out of evil will, and action results in evil consequences.

Of the four above mentioned types of behaviour, it is apparent that type (1) is good, while type (4) is bad. However, there is problem in type (2) and type (3) behaviours as they cannot be clearly said whether they are good or bad and hence controversy may arise over the notion of good and bad.

Those who accept that the behaviour is bad, if the result is bad though the motive is good and the behaviour is good if the result is good though the motive is bad are based entirely on the consequence disregarding the motive. The ethical conducts based on such perceptions are philosophically termed Teleological ethics.

On the other hand, there are some who believe that the behaviour is good if the motive is good, though the consequence is bad and the behaviour is bad if the motive is bad, though the motive is good. Such perceptions are essentially based on the motive, disregarding the consequence. The ethical conducts that emphasize the importance of motive have led to the emergence of Formalistic ethics.

There are some sayings in Myanmar tradition concerned with speech. "Telling the right words is a truth" and this saying is essentially based on this good and right action and thus is a manifestation of formalism.

Another Myanmar saying related to speech is that "Want to be loved; it depends on the four finger-breadths of the mouth and so does to be hated". This saying highlights the importance of consequence and hence included in consequentialism. The love and hatred of other can be created by the speech which comes out of the mouth that has a breadth of four fingers. If someone wants to be loved by others he must speak sweetly and gently which is right and good by nature. In this case, the saying focuses solely on the consequence.

Other such saying as "Be sweet is speech and be loved by others", "sweet speech leads to accomplishment" and "Good mouth can rule the notion" are all intended to get good consequences. Therefore, Myanmar ethical attitudes of speeches are a blend of formalism and teleological which are somehow contradictory. The good and bad of ethical conducts are not taken as being fixed, but accept and practise then in accord with the situation. In determining the right or wrong and the good and bad, Myanmar ethical concepts are adjusted with time, place and situation, not depending solely either on formalism or consequentialism.

According to the *Theravāda* Buddhist standpoint, right understanding (*samaditthi*) gives rise to right thought which includes from perceiving worldly things objectively to insight that realizes the absolute truth (*ariya sacca*). Since it analyses and accept only that are rational, *Theravada* Buddhism is known as "*Vibhajjavāda*"

According to the Buddha, however a speech may be right and good, one should hold one's tongue, unless it is deemed ineffective. One should first try to get all the information and analyze them before speaking something to someone. One should speak only when one realizes that the speech may yield good result or favourable response There are several Buddha's teaching in regard with speech.

Conclusion

Myanmar ethical conduct is largely based on Theravada Buddhism and is based on reasoning which accepts the good and the bad only after analysis. But it also avoids dogmatism because according to Buddhism nothing is permanent. According to Buddha, any action must be done with good will, simultaneously taking into consideration the consequences of the action. To be able to adjust to a situation, one needs intelligence that can weigh the pros and cons outcome of an action. The implies the importance of consequence and of oneself.

Therefore, in conduction any bodily or verbal action, not only good will but also its consequence are important. One should employ reasoning that analyse the situation objectively. Then only an action be free from misdeed and bring about good consequences.

In brief, the Myanmar human society which is highly influenced by Buddhist teaching accepts both formalism and consequentialism which are contradictory to each other. Myanmar people do not practise the fixed good and bad ideas of ethical conducts, but they act in conformity with time and place.

Buddhism accepts rationalism after analysing the formalism and consequentialism in accord with time and place. It, in fact, is based on rationalism.

When *Shuba*, the son of *Tawdaeya* asked Buddha which was more virtuous between the life of a *bhikkhu* and a layman. Buddha said, "Oh man, I speak anything only after analysing. I am not used to speaking definitely over something. According to Buddha there is no such speech that should be taken it for granted forever. Buddha did not preach with one-sided view, but only that seemed to be appropriate to the time and situation."

Myanmar ethical conducts are based on *Theravada* Buddhism and practised rationalism which accepts the good and the bad conducts only after analysis, not taking as being unchangeable.

By practising rationalism in ethical conducts, any action must be done with good will, simultaneously taking consideration on the consequence of the action. To be able to adjust a situation, one needs intelligence that can weigh the pros and cons of the outcome of the action. Intelligence is the key to morality. Buddha's ethical conducts are not either for oneself or others, but for both.

In *Salawatupana sutta, Anguttaa Nikaya, Catukanipata*, the Buddha said. The one who looks for the benefit of others and not for oneself is better than the one who looks neither oneself nor for others. The one who is better than that person is the one who looks for oneself but not for other. Among the three persons the one who is for oneself and others is the best.

This implies the importance of consequence and of oneself. Therefore, in conducting any bodily or verbal action, not only good will but also its consequence are important. One should accept and practise rationalism that analyses the situation objectively. Then only may an action be free from misdeed and bring good consequence. The moral conducts that should be practised for the benefit of human society are important together with intellect that can rationalize the existing situations.

Acknowledgements

I would like to my thanks to Dr Aye Aye Tun (Rector) and Dr Yin Yin Than (Pro- Rector) Bago University. And then I am also grateful to Dr Myint Myint Soe (professor), Philosophy Department.

References

- Bonhoeffer, Dietrich. (1955). *Ethics*. London: SCM Press Ltd.
- Department for the Promotion and Propagation of the Sasana. (2002). *How to Live as A Good Buddhist*. Vol. I. Translated by U Han Htay & U Chit.
- Dhammananda, K. Sri. (1993). *What Buddhists Believe*. (Firth Edition) The Corporate Body of the Buddha Education Foundation.
- Kalupahana, D. J. (1976). *Buddhist Philosophy*. Hawaii: The University Press of Hawaii.
- Ledi Sayadaw, Mahathera. (1981). *The Manuals of Buddhism*. Translated by the English Editorial Board Yangon: Department of Religious Affairs.
- Narada. (1988). *The Buddha and His Teachings*. Kuala Lumpur: Buddhist Missionary.
- Tachibana, S. (1926). *The Ethics of Buddhism*. London: curzon press Ltd.
- Thittila, Ashin. (1987). *Essential Themes of Buddhist Lectures*. Rangoon: Department of Religious Affairs.
- Titus, Harold H. (1996). *Ethics for Today*. (Third Edition) New Delhi: Eurasia Publishing House (Pvt, Ltd. Ram Nager).